

DIAGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF ERYTHROCYTE SEDIMENTATION RATE AND C-REACTIVE PROTEIN IN THE PROGNOSIS OF THE COURSE OF NONSPECIFIC AORTOARTERITIS

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Morphological studies have proved that nonspecific aortoarteritis (NAA) is a granulomatous vasculitis of large vessels of autoimmune origin, which dynamically leads to stenoses, occlusions or aneurysmal dilations of the aorta and its branches, in most cases – subclavian, common carotid arteries with a wavy course and alternating active and inactive stages of the process. Treatment of NAA is complex – conservative (glucocorticosteroids, cytostatics, targeted cytokine inhibitors) and operative (reconstruction of arteries to eliminate clinically significant stenoses of the branches of the aortic arch). At the same time, surgical intervention in the acute stage of NAA is associated with worse results, and markers for separation at the NAA stage are under study and have not been definitively determined.

Materials and methods. A single-center cohort analytical study of patients with NAA with lesions of the branches of the aortic arch who were examined and treated at the State Institution "Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Surgery named after academician V. Vakhidov" from 1978 to 2021 was conducted, a total of 300 patients, 272 of them women, the average age of patients was 31.06 ± 0.53 years.

The results and their discussion. We attempted to determine the cut-off thresholds for some laboratory markers of inflammation in patients with NAA, depending on the results of treatment. We considered the absence of progression involving new domains and vessels in NAA to be a favorable outcome (intermediate point), the presence of progression to be unfavorable. As our observations showed, the level of leukocytosis before the intervention, as well as the content of the acute phase protein fibrinogen, was not associated with the outcome of treatment, whereas for C-reactive protein and ESR ROC, the analysis showed the presence of such a relationship, and the tests themselves can be regarded as informative in the prognosis of treatment. These thresholds were the following – ESR less than 32 mm/h, C-reactive protein less than 18

mg/l at AUC = 0.905 (S=81%, S=90%) and 0.902 (S=95%, S=75%), respectively, associated with a favorable outcome of conservative treatment and surgery. A decrease in ESR and C-reactive protein were associated with a favorable outcome of surgical treatment – with good late bypass patency: the thresholds were as follows – ESR less than 21 mm/h, C-reactive protein less than 11 mg/l at AUC = 0.91 (H=90%, C=85%) and AUC =0.88 (H=95%, C=80%), respectively. In the long-term period after prolongation of methotrexate therapy, the levels of C-reactive protein and ESR decreased to 6.58 ± 0.29 mg/l and 13.0 ± 0.35 mm/h, whereas against the background of glucocorticosteroid treatment, these indicators were 9.0 ± 0.4 mg/l and 18.4 ± 0.5 mm/h, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion. Threshold levels for laboratory remission of nonspecific aortoarteritis: ESR less than 21 mm/h, C-reactive protein less than 11 mg/l

